

AI-Driven Autonomous Platforms for Nanomaterial Discovery and Optimization: Bridging Simulation, Synthesis, and In Situ Characterization

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Abstract. Next-generation autonomous labs that integrate machine learning, robotic synthesis, and in-situ characterization are emerging as one of the most transformative directions in modern materials science. By combining active and deep learning algorithms with multi-level datasets ranging from quantum mechanical simulations to high-throughput flow-based experiments, they are creating closed-loop theory-experiment frameworks capable of guiding complex nanofabrication processes in real time. These AI-driven platforms reduce material consumption and energy costs, enable the targeted design of nanostructures with customized optical, electronic, and mechanical properties, and open up possibilities that were considered unattainable just a few years ago. This review presents a comprehensive analysis of the current state of self-driving laboratories (SDLs), their architectural frameworks, algorithmic approaches, and practical demonstrations, including the optimization of perovskite nanostructures, the development of nanoparticles for targeted drug delivery, and the synthesis of quantum dots with controlled emission. It will also explore existing methodological gaps, data standards, and challenges in the integration of in situ characterization techniques, and discuss the prospects for establishing fully digital material production pipelines, similar to recent autonomous laboratory demonstrations that progressed from initial hypothesis to functional prototypes within exceptionally short timeframes.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence; Machine learning; Self-driving labs; Autonomous material discovery; Nanomaterials; In-situ characterization; Inverse design; Bayesian optimization; Reinforcement learning; Digital twins; Explainable AI.

In recent years, artificial intelligence has evolved from a complementary tool for data analysis to an important driver of progress in materials science and nanotechnology, especially in combination with autonomous laboratories [1-4]. SDLs integrate robotic synthesis modules, versatile in-situ characterization systems, and machine learning algorithms, ranging from generative models to Bayesian optimization and reinforcement learning [5-7]. A key advantage of these systems is the implementation of a closed-loop workflow: automatic generation of hypotheses, experimental design, synthesis, data acquisition and analysis, and formulation of the next experimental step without human intervention [8-10]. This approach not only speeds up the research cycle, but also improves the reproducibility and overall quality of the data obtained. A notable example is the A-Lab platform, developed at the Lawrence Berkeley National Laboratory, which demonstrated the first fully autonomous solid-state synthesis of inorganic compounds [11]. Algorithms process extensive literature data together with results from density functional theory (DFT) calculations to develop an optimal synthesis plan, operate robotic dispensers and furnaces, analyze powder diffraction data in real time using machine learning models [12-14]. This integration enables the discovery of previously unknown phases within days, whereas conventional approaches often take weeks or months. The system has already been successfully

used to synthesize complex oxides, including materials with promising thermoelectric properties [12].

In parallel, the integration of flow chemistry into SDL is progressing rapidly. Flow reactors provide continuous control over reaction composition and synthesis conditions, increase operational flexibility, and significantly increase experimental data density [14]. In the study by Delgado-Licona et al [15], the use of dynamic flow conditions in autonomous quantum dot synthesis increased the amount of usable data by more than an order of magnitude, enabling rapid identification of optimal conditions to achieve the targeted size distribution and spectral properties. The AlphaFlow platform combines microfluidic channels with Bayesian optimization and active learning, allowing multi-step reactions to be performed with precise parameter control at each stage [16].

In-situ and in-operando techniques are becoming integral components of such systems. Machine learning algorithms that drive X-ray diffraction, Raman spectroscopy, or absorption spectroscopy can focus measurements on the most informative spectral or angular regions, reducing overall experiment time and minimizing instrument load [17,18]. Liang and co-workers [19] have implemented a real-time closed loop between theory and experiment, in which synthesis results immediately influence the parameters of the subsequent reaction without human intervention. This capability is particularly important when working with metastable nanophases and reactions with narrow process windows. The use of generative models for inverse design has attracted a lot of attention. Instead of testing countless combinations, the researcher specifies the target properties, such as the band gap energy or absorption coefficient, and the model generates structures that are likely to have these properties. Manica et al [20] presented the Generative Toolkit for Scientific Discovery (GT4SD), an extensible open-source library for the design of organic materials that has been experimentally validated [20]. Pyzer-Knapp et al [21] offered a comprehensive perspective on basic modelling in materials science, covering applications from property prediction to molecular generation [21]. Recently, Zeni et al [22] presented MatterGen, a diffusion-based generative model for the inverse design of inorganic materials, and demonstrated the synthesis of a generated structure whose properties were within 20% of the target [22].

Despite this progress, significant challenges remain. One major problem is the lack of widely accepted standards for the visualization and exchange of data. Laboratories often use incompatible formats, which hinders the integration of simulators, robotic systems, and AI modules. The MGI workshop report [23] emphasizes the need to standardize data formats and APIs, and to develop a digital infrastructure that ensures the interoperability of platforms. Another challenge is explainability (XAI). Without transparent justifications for AI-generated decisions, adoption in areas that require rigorous validation, such as pharmaceuticals or nuclear energy, is difficult [24]. In addition, cybersecurity concerns are becoming increasingly important: SDLs are often connected to networks, making them vulnerable to disruption and data breaches, including the compromise of intellectual property [25-28].

In the next five to ten years, SDLs are expected to evolve into fully functional digital twins of laboratories and production lines, that can model and optimize not only synthesis processes but also industrial manufacturing [26]. This integration would combine basic discovery, prototyping, and large-scale production into a single automated pipeline. Work is already underway to adapt SDLs for quantum electronics, nanophonics, and nanomedicine. These include the autonomous optimization of defects in diamond nitrogen-vacancy (NV) centers, the design of negative refractive index metamaterials and the development of nanoparticles for targeted drug delivery with programmable pharmacokinetics [27-35]. These developments bring us closer to the moment when an autonomous platform acts as a "scientific co-author", generating ideas, designing experiments, interpreting results, and even preparing patent applications.

Conflicts of interest.

The authors declare no conflicts of interest of relevance to this topic.

Author's contributions

The first author conducted the literature search in Scopus, Web of Science, and publisher databases; preprints were screened on arXiv. Both authors contributed equally to the conceptual discussion, literature analysis, manuscript preparation, review, and editing. No AI tools were used in the preparation of this work.

Data availability statement

Not applicable: No new data was generated or analyzed.

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